

Diabetes UK

Data management plan required?	Encouraged - Applicants should ensure that responsibilities relating to data collection, storage, verification and security are assigned to an individual with appropriate expertise in data management.(For applications that require statistical analysis)
RDM policy Link	No
Definition of data	Not specified
Length of data management plan	Not specified
DMP template/ requirements	Not specified
Required data repository	Not specified
Time for data release	Not specified
Time for long-term storage of data	Not specified
Costings	Not specified
Last updated	Not known
Contact Details	research@diabetes.org.uk
Comments	N/A

Documents used:

Tips on writing a grant application

<https://www.diabetes.org.uk/research/for-researchers/apply-for-a-grant/general-guidelines-for-grant-applicants/tips-on-writing-a-grant-application>

Accessed: May 2018